

Site detection across Europe and the HillfortFinderApp – latest results from a Deep Learning based hillfort search

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Abstract

The widely increasing availability and improving resolution of LiDAR data are revolutionising landscape archaeology, allowing the identification of previously unknown archaeological features and thus aiding research as well as heritage protection strategies. This can be achieved even on a countrywide scale by using effective automation techniques. Our work aims at developing an approach to automatically detect hillfort sites cross-regionally, using Britain to train a neural network tool and Italy and Germany to test its transferability to different regions and landscapes.

Hillforts are amongst the most evident and iconic archaeological sites in Europe. Usually associated with the Iron Age, they can date from the Neolithic to early Medieval times. The Atlas of Hillforts (Lock and Ralston 2017) provides a comprehensive and up-to-date record of these sites, over 4000 in total, and an invaluable database for further research (e.g., Maddison 2022).

The large number of hillforts known in Britain constitutes the best training dataset available to date for developing effective automation for recognising hillforts in remotely sensed data. The variety of landscapes present in Italy and Germany, on the other hand, makes these areas an optimal case study for testing the transferability of this type of automation in different regions.

Keywords: Landscape Archaeology; Automated detection; Hillforts; LiDAR; CNN; Machine Learning.

1. Introduction and previous work

Since 2020, we have been developing a Neural Network to automatically detect hillforts in Britain from LiDAR data. The methodology and the workflow have already been presented at various conferences (see Landauer and Verschoof-van der Vaart 2021). In this paper we focus on three novel enhancements based on our previous research. First, we describe a workflow that allows the application of automatic hillfort detection to very large areas, even on a regional or countrywide scale (section 2 for technology and methods used, section 3 for a discussion of results from England). Secondly, we examine how our method can be applied to other regions outside Britain: In section 4 we describe the modifications needed to apply the method to landscapes that are substantially different to the one our neural network was originally trained on. Then we discuss what results we found by applying our method to the German state of Hesse (section 5) and the Molise region in Italy (section 6).

2. Technology: AI architecture and landscape-wide search

The Artificial Intelligence based architecture of our method has already been discussed in detail in our earlier publication (Landauer and Verschoof-van der Vaart 2021), but for easier reading we summarise it as follows: We trained a Neural Network using a modern ConvNeXT architecture (Liu et al. 2020) with LiDAR vignettes of known hillforts in England as positive samples, and random vignettes of land not containing hillforts as negative samples. This resulted in a classifier function that can efficiently analyse any LiDAR vignette of the same size (we use 512 x 512 m²) and assign a confidence value between 0 and 100 percent of this vignette containing a hillfort.

We have since developed this workflow further, as we are interested in applying the classifier to very large land areas, even on a regional or countrywide level. We do this by splitting the region of interest into a grid of LiDAR vignettes and presenting each to the classifier for evaluation. The output is a grid of coordinates of that region where each grid point has a confidence or probability of this point being near a possible hillfort assigned to it.

Note that this causes a computational challenge; England, for example, with an area of more than 240,000 km² has a total of 266 GB of data available. Moreover, in our setup this means that some 1.9 million LiDAR patches need to be processed; we found empirically that overlapping vignettes to a denser grid size of approximately one third of its dimension (we use 150 m) performs substantially better than the default 512 m grid.

In order to bring the processing times down to reasonable levels on a mid-range PC with a 12-core CPU we use the *Multiprocessing* package of Pytorch (Paszke et al. 2019) for loading and pre-processing LiDAR data. In addition, we run the neural network prediction solely on its Nvidia RTX 2060 graphics system which further speeds up the process. By doing so, we can now process all of the available English data within eight hours.

Additionally, we now follow a crowd sourcing approach by introducing a web application named “HillfortFinderApp”. Archaeologists are invited to upload LiDAR tiles from their region to the WWW and get a list of possible hillfort sites within these tiles and their confidence scores in return.

Optionally, they can provide feedback on the detection quality by indicating false positives. These could then in turn be used to fine-tune the neural network, thus contributing to a stepwise improvement process. The app is available to the public on this URL: <http://bit.ly/findforts>

3. Proposed workflow for efficient validation: Results from Northern England

As presented at CAA22, an earlier trial was conducted over the Chilterns in southern England. This area had been the subject of a Citizen Science archaeology project, with high resolution LiDAR made available via an interactive website (<https://www.chilternsaonb.org/flagship-projects/beacons-of-the-past/>). Most importantly for us was their discovery of a previously unrecognized hillfort, Figure 1, whose location is still confidential. This was not only a ‘proving ground’ for the technology, but also for developing a systematic and efficient workflow for processing the AI output. We were able to independently identify this hillfort, and had this confirmed it with the Chilterns project team (pers.comm.).

Figure 1: previously unrecognized English hillfort, independently identified in 2022

Following this success, an AI detection was conducted over a selected area of Northern England, as shown in Figure 2. There was a substantial but not complete coverage of LiDAR for this area, as England is not yet fully complete (<https://environment.data.gov.uk/>). This was a new area for investigation, and one where there is a relatively low density of known hillforts, from the Atlas (<https://hillforts.arch.ox.ac.uk/>).

Figure 2: area of study, showing known hillforts from the Atlas in purple (<https://environment.data.gov.uk/>)

Known hillforts from the Atlas were excluded, and 1500 samples, covering some 7000 km² were generated from 66% probability upwards. Clearly analysis could not be conducted where LiDAR was missing, namely the white sections in Figure 2. Each sample was provided with a 512 x 512 m² LiDAR hillshade vignette, with the probability, x and y coordinates (GB Grid), tile name (Ordnance Survey identifier) and the minimum distance to a known hillfort all provided as a CSV file. This data was also encoded within the vignette file name.

104 **3.1. Procedure**

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106 The procedure for processing outputs is illustrated below, Figure 3, with a possible site being identified
107 from LiDAR. The vignette is then manually inspected for possible features of interest. In this case, an
108 online map is viewed, and then a map-based search carried out on the Historic Environment Record
109 (HER) (<https://www.heritagegateway.org.uk/gateway/>). Items from the specific HER search are then
110 checked.
111

112
113 **Figure 3:** illustration of the procedure for processing the AI output

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115
116 The data was imported into a working Excel file, and broken into the classifications: 90-100%, 85-90%,
117 80-85%, 75-80%, 70-75% and 66-70%.

118 The analysis was divided into two parts for each of these groups. The first stage was a visual inspection
119 of the vignette, and a classification into categories was recorded in the worksheet using a pull-down list.
120 The time of start and finish was recorded, to the nearest minute, and the time per vignette calculated.
121 The classifications are only approximate. 'Gully' covers a wide range of possibilities including inland
122 cliffs, river gullies and so on. 'Enclosure' was self-evident. 'Interesting' was something not obviously
123 an enclosure but worthy of further investigation.

124 This classification could be done quite quickly with Excel doing auto-completion after the single use of
125 a category. Note that on the third % group this classification process was dropped, and only the 'enclo-
126 sure' and 'interesting' categories recorded, as there was no use being made of the others. This speeded
127 up the process, as can be seen later.

128 The second stage was to copy all the results into a second worksheet for this particular % grouping. A
129 filter was then applied and the classes 'interesting' and 'enclosure' selected.

130 The 'interesting' and 'enclosure' vignettes were then copied into separate folders respectively.

131 The filtered results in the spreadsheet were sorted on the basis of x then y coordinates, to provide group-
132 ing of duplicates where they occurred. The coordinates were also formatted for direct entry into the
133 online map search function (<https://www.streetmap.co.uk/>).

134 The second stage analysis then started.

135 **Step 1:** copy the “x,y” coordinates into the Streetmap search function (<https://www.streetmap.co.uk/>);
 136 zoom to the location and look for any recorded features. Note that it is not directly possible to use
 137 Ordnance Survey (OS) online (<https://explore.osmaps.com/>) as it requires the OS grid coordinates to
 138 conduct the search. Conversion would be time consuming and unnecessary, see below.

139 **Step 2:** convert the coordinates using the Streetmap ‘convert’ function; this gives OS grid coordinates,
 140 and Lat Long, as well as other location data.

141 **Step 3:** depending on the nature of the result, search in the Historic Environment portal using either the
 142 x,y or OS grid coordinates, and search for records within 250m-1000m of the location, depending on
 143 the density of records. Occasionally a search was made on Google Earth using the Lat/Long. In most
 144 cases this was either not necessary or provided no useful information, particularly where the feature was
 145 under tree cover.

146 **Step 4:** record a summary of findings in the ‘notes’ column of the worksheet.

147 One important point to note regarding the process of interpreting the vignettes is that the human recog-
 148 nition of a feature may not actually be the same as that generated by the AI process. Where likely, this
 149 was noted against the individual result.

150 3.2. Results

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 152 Results of the work, broken down for each % group are summarised below, Figure 4. This includes the
 153 timings for each group, by each stage.

154 Note that there was some additional set up time, particularly in the beginning, as well as additional time
 155 at the end to summarise the results, and write them up.

156

% group	# samples	Stage 1 total time hr:min	Stage 1/ sample time min:sec	Stage 2 samples encl.	Stage 2 samples int'ing	Stage 2 samples total	sample ratio %	Stage 2 total time hrs:min	Stage 2/ sample time min:sec	Results
90-100%	89	00:17	00:11	8	16	24	27%	01:37	04:02	No candidates
85-90%	168	00:31	00:11	11	18	29	17%	01:27	03:00	Two candidate enclosures, each from one sample
80-85%	235	00:18	00:04	5	6	11	5%	00:23	02:05	no candidates
75-80%	285	00:07	00:01	8	0	8	3%	00:05	00:37	One candidate enclosure
70-75%	377	00:13	00:02	13	1	14	4%	00:49	03:30	Two candidate enclosures, one from two samples. This latter is auxiliary to a recorded medieval site
66-70%	346	00:15	00:02	8	1	9	3%	00:30	03:20	One candidate enclosure from a single sample
TOTALS	1500	01:41		53	42	95		04:51		
Average			00:04						03:03	

158 **Figure 4:** Summary of results
 159
 160

3.3. Timings

The total recorded timings were 6:32 hours. Probably another 2 hours were involved in various setting up activities, excluding the time to write up the results, making a total of about 8:30 hours.

The average time per stage was 4 seconds per vignette and 3 mins 03 seconds per identified candidate. These times speeded up through the process, as a result of streamlining and experience.

The ratio of candidates from samples, reduced through the probability bands, but notably a candidate was still found at 66-70% probability. This is unsurprising given the extensive knowledge of the landscape that has accumulated in Britain over the past 2-3 centuries.

4. Moving on to other regions: Dealing with the Model Drift problem

Initial attempts to apply the Neural Network classifier trained with English hillforts on foreign landscapes yielded poor detection results. This is in line with an observation well documented in literature: the so-called "Model Drift". Using Neural Networks for data (here: land patches in LiDAR) somewhat different from the original training data usually results in a greatly reduced performance of the Neural Network. In our case this is caused by differences in LiDAR scan equipment used, different landscape patterns, and a different stochastic distribution of the elevation values found in the data. Various approaches to deal with this problem have been proposed (see Xu et al. 2023 for a recent overview), but a rather easy to implement approach already provided good results here: we took the model trained on England and fine-tuned it (i.e., re-trained it for a few epochs, here: 7) with some random data from another region we were interested in.

Table 5 demonstrates this using the Molise example (see section 6 below): by fine-tuning with 8,000 randomly chosen patches of LiDAR from Molise the detection rate (precision) of known forts increased from 46% to 65%. Then, by adding merely 20 forts to the fine-tuning data as positive examples, the rate increased to 85%. Both experiments excluded the 20 known forts used for training from the evaluation.

Model fine-tuned on	Known forts found
England only	46 %
England + 8,000 random patches from Molise	65 %
England + 8,000 random patches from Molise + 20 known forts from Molise	85 %

Table 5: stepwise improvement with fine-tuning using local landscape data

5. Results from an entire state in Germany: Hesse

The state of Hesse is situated more or less in the centre of Europe and is one of the larger German federal states with a size of 21,115.63 km² (figure 6). Its landscapes are characterized by a wider heterogeneity of different environmental zones, divided in 59 main natural regions (Hauptnaturreaumzonen), including flat regions like the flood plains of the river Rhine in the south, undulating terrains with fertile soils like the Wetterau in the centre and mountainous areas like the Taunus, the Vogelsberg, or the Odenwald

197 (Fig. 7 left). Hesse has the second largest share of forested areas in Germany, 8,415.62 km², equalling
198 42.3% were covered by forests in 2021 (Fig. 7 right; <https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Branchen-Unternehmen/Landwirtschaft-Forstwirtschaft-Fischerei/Wald-Holz/Tabellen/waldflaeche-bundeslaender.html>).
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Figure 6: The German state of Hesse in Europe (SRTM USGS-authored or produced data and information are in the public domain).

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Figure 7: Known hillforts in the state of Hesse. Left: Green lines mark the 59 different main natural regions within Hesse. Right: Green areas mark the forests (SRTM USGS-authored or produced data and information are in the public domain; natural regions BFN; forests GDS Hessen).

211 As most of the hillforts have survived underneath the forest canopy, the landscapes of Hesse – though
212 rather heterogeneous – offer good chances to discover three-dimensional relics of archaeological fea-
213 tures like burial mounds or ditches and ramparts of (prehistoric) hillforts, especially as the LiDAR da-
214 taset of the complete state is available in a 1m resolution (<https://gds.hessen.de>).
215 To feed the model, more than 100 known hillfort sites have been used as training data with the process
216 outlined in the previous section. Calculating the area of the state took about 6 hours and resulted in
217 99,836 findings of potential hillforts. These have been narrowed down to 106 findings with a confidence
218 value of > 0.94 (Figure 8).
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220
221 **Figure 8:** Potential hillforts sites with a confidence value of > 0.94 in the state of Hesse. (SRTM
222 USGS-authored or produced data and information are in the public domain).
223

224 In order to evaluate these findings, they were loaded into QGIS as 512 x 512 m² vignettes of hillshade
225 terrain models of the classified area (Fig. 9).
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Figure 9: Hillshade DEM vignette of a potential hillfort site (DEM: HVBG).

231 The candidates were classified according to their potential likeliness of containing a (prehistoric) hillfort
232 (Table 10) as well as to the potential reasons of those areas for being classified as hillforts (Table 11).
233 The basis for the ‘manual’ evaluation were various LiDAR DEM visualisations (hillshading, hillshading
234 from multiple directions, simple local relief model, sky view factor; all calculated with the Relief Visu-
235 alisation Toolbox (RVT; Kokalj/Hesse 2017, <https://www.zrc-sazu.si/en/rvt>) plugin for QGIS, as well
236 as the digital orthophotos of the state of Hesse, Open Street Map and Wikipedia (mainly for the evalua-
237 tion of potential castle/chateaux sites). Online access to the state heritage database was not yet available
238 but would have made the work far more effective. The 106 candidates could be checked and also clas-
239 sified in about two hours’ time (Fig. 12).

240

evaluation	number
castles/chateaux	25
correct positives (unknown)	0
correct positives (known)	4
false positives	57
unclear (likely)	1
unclear (maybe)	9
unclear (unlikely)	10

106

241 **Table 10:** Classification of the potential hillfort likeliness of findings with a confidence value > 0.94.
242

class	number	number (false positives only)
field/forest boundaries	11	8
field terraces	19	12
forest paths	49	37
terrain features	49	37
quarries	7	6
modern features	2	2
castles/chateaux	25	-

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243 **Table 11:** Classification of the potential reasons for areas being classified as hillforts (multiple entries,
244 e.g., field terraces & forest paths, are possible)
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Figure 12: Classification of the likeliness of hillfort findings

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250 No clear unknown hillfort sites have been detected – which is most likely due to the fact that most if not
251 all ‘detectable’ hillforts (i.e., those that left clear three-dimensional traces of ditches, ramparts or walls
252 in today’s terrain) are already known to the heritage authorities. However, one site was classified as
253 ‘unclear (likely)’ and nine others as ‘unclear (maybe)’ – which means, that there is still the potential of
254 finding new hillfort sites in Hesse. These ten sites also show the problems in detecting hillfort (and
255 other) sites in the LiDAR data in general: some features and structures do look like they could possibly
256 relate to a hillfort but the evidence is not clear enough to be certain. Whilst this is of course not only a
257 problem of interpreting LiDAR data, it is surely also true for ‘ground truthing’ these sites, as fieldwalk-
258 ing and even excavations do not always reveal an uncontested result. The main advances of using Li-
259 DAR data – and especially models using AI algorithms – is the speed of the process of searching com-
260 plete landscapes for three-dimensional archaeological structures.

261 The AI did find castles and chateaux – once the building structures are erased from the DSM, leaving
262 the DTM data only, those sites simply appear very similar in the LiDAR data to prehistoric hillforts.
263 This however proves the capability of the chosen AI algorithm for the purpose.

264 More than 50% of the 106 evaluated sites turned out to be false positives, which seems to be a rather
265 high share. One reason is the fact that a number are other features, mainly forest paths and terrain fea-
266 tures (Fig. 13). These structures often appear as circular features, surrounding a hill and therefore are
267 very similar to a ditch and rampart system, which also usually follows the contour lines around a hill or
268 a plateau (Fig. 14). Training non-sites with similar examples might help to enhance the algorithm’s
269 quality.

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Figure 13: Potential reasons for addressing vignettes as hillforts (left columns: total, right columns: false positives only)

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Figure 14: Example of a false positive candidate, most likely wrongly classified due to existing forest paths and terrain structures (DEM: HVBG).

279 Another potential reason for falsely positive classified vignettes was the fact that an unvalidated file of
280 hillfort sites was used for training the model. After rechecking each findspot it became clear that the file
281 included a number of sites that no longer existed when the LiDAR data was derived in 2021, mainly
282 because they were destroyed by quarrying in the 19th and 20th century. A few sites have been wrongly

283 located or were only known from historical sources but not been checked in the terrain. After deleting
 284 these ‘false knowns’ a new set of 94 sites will be used as training data for a new model.
 285 One other fact might also have led to a false classification as a hillfort: the variety and heterogeneity of
 286 hillforts regarding their shapes, sizes and placements within their surrounding landscapes (Fig. 15) might
 287 make it difficult to find similarities that can be used as a basis for a sound classification of landscape
 288 features as a hillfort (Posluschny 2019; Posluschny 2022). Increasing the number of training data sites
 289 could be a solution to overcome this issue, however, this might not be possible if – as in the state of
 290 Hesse – the sites used to train the algorithm include all known hillforts and the number of so-far unde-
 291 tected hillfort sites is potentially near to zero.
 292

293 **Figure 15:** Differing shapes and sizes of prehistoric hillforts in Hesse (same scale).
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297 **6. Moving to Italy: Results from Molise**

298 **6.1 Study region**

299 The region of Molise, Italy, constitutes an interesting case study for testing the transferability of the AI
 300 classifier in a Mediterranean context. The region covers a transect of the Italian territory, running from
 301 the Adriatic coast to the central Apennine Mountain range. The landscape varies, starting from the gentle
 302 hilly terrain of the coastal area and transitioning to the rugged mountainous regions of the Apennines.
 303 Consequentially, the vegetation also significantly changes, ranging from broad-leaved deciduous plants
 304 in the mountains to evergreen and deciduous species, shrublands, and Mediterranean maquis in the
 305 plains.
 306

307 During the pre-Roman and Medieval periods, the region witnessed settlements in hillfort sites that varied
 308 significantly in size, typology, and location. The Ancient Hillforts Survey (AHS) recently conducted an
 309

310 analysis of the entire territory using LiDAR data provided by the Italian Ministry of the Environment
 311 (Ministero dell'ambiente e della tutela del territorio e del mare) (Costabile, Cocco, and Petriglia 2013)).
 312 In this study, the point cloud data provided by the government was reprocessed to generate a 1m reso-
 313 lution Digital Elevation Model (DEM) specifically designed for archaeological purposes. Subsequently,
 314 the area was visually interpreted, leading to the identification of several hundred potential hillforts, out
 315 of which more than one hundred were subsequently validated in the field (Fontana 2022).
 316 This new dataset represents an excellent opportunity to test the effectiveness of the AI classifier in de-
 317 tecting hillfort sites and compare it with traditional methods of visual interpretation. Furthermore, the
 318 field data provides a reliable means to verify whether the AI-detected anomalies correspond to actual
 319 archaeological features.

320

321 **6.2 Results and discussion**

322

323 The analysis was conducted using the same in-house generated DEM (Digital Elevation Model) used
 324 for interpretation by the AHS. The calculation took less than an hour and resulted in 369 detections. The
 325 first 100, with a confidence value above 0.94, were manually validated using a combination of AHS
 326 data, modified VAT LiDAR visualization (Kokalj and Somrak 2019), and aerial and satellite imagery.
 327 Unlike the UK, there were no comprehensive national databases available.

328 Table 16 presents the classification of the top 100 detections. Fifteen of these correspond to confirmed
 329 hillforts, while the remaining 85 are categorized as different types of false positives. Figure 1 illustrates
 330 how the AI classifier successfully detected various hillfort typologies, including sites with varying sizes,
 331 numbers of fortification vallations, and locations in the landscape, such as contour or promontory hill-
 332 forts.

333

Detections	
True positives	15
False positives	85
Detections by type	
Hillforts	15
Villages	10
Field systems	10
Terrain features	65

334

335 **Table 16:** Classification of the top 100 detections corresponding to confidence value above 0.94.

336

337 Among the false positives, ten modern villages were identified as hillforts. These villages are actually
 338 medieval hillforts situated on hilltops that have continued to be inhabited up to modern times. Today,
 339 they are characterized by a modern road that surrounds the summit just outside the ancient fortifications.
 340 As for the cases of the false positives identified in Hesse, these detections appear as approximately
 341 circular features encircling a hill, resembling the ditch and rampart system typical of hillfort sites. A
 342 similar appearance is observed in ten other false positives, which are actually field systems. These field
 343 systems often appear as terrace walls following the contour lines around a hill, enclosing it. Terrain
 344 features were the most common among the false positives identified, likely due to the extensive moun-
 345 tainous areas in the Molise region. These features typically include spurs or hill summits with steep
 346 cliffs, where the steepness of the cliff demarcates the summit areas in a manner comparable to the an-
 347 thropogenic features described above. These observations confirm the patterns identified in Hesse, em-
 348 phasizing the importance of training the AI classifier with non-site examples that resemble these dis-
 349 tinctive yet common natural features.

350 Looking at the false positives, we can identify two main reasons why these sites were not detected, both
351 related to the characteristic landscapes of the Mediterranean regions. First, hillforts in the region are
352 often integrated into intricate terrace systems, which are typical features of Italian and Mediterranean
353 areas. The density of these terraces, constructed along the orientation of pre-existing circuits, poses a
354 challenge even for human interpreters in identifying these sites. Therefore, it is not surprising that the
355 AI classifier encounters limitations in these areas (refer to Figure 17, left).

356 Secondly, many areas in the Mediterranean are covered by dense maquis vegetation, which is a distinct
357 characteristic. This vegetation can be extremely dense, making the effectiveness of standard LiDAR
358 flights significantly lower in creating accurate models, compared to LiDAR acquisitions in temperate
359 Europe and the British Isles. Consequently, hillfort sites often become masked by noise in the LiDAR
360 data, complicating their interpretation (refer to Figure 18, right).

361 These two observations highlight the need to implement new training areas in the AI classifier to account
362 for these specific landscapes that differ the most from the ones the classifier was originally trained on.
363 Furthermore, it also underscores an intrinsic limitation of LiDAR data. While we can anticipate that the
364 ever-increasing quality of available LiDAR data will compensate for areas with dense vegetation, such
365 as in the case of Mediterranean maquis, the presence of hillforts and other sites in terraced landscapes
366 remains an open issue that has yet to be extensively addressed in archaeological research.

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Figure 17: Examples of hillforts correctly detected by the AI classifier.

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375 **Figure 18:** Examples of false negatives related to the characteristics terraced (left) and maquis land-
376 scapes of the Mediterranean (right). The black triangles indicate the fortification circuits of the hill-
377 forts.

378 7. Conclusion

379 This research contributes to automating the detection of previously unknown archaeological sites in
380 three ways. First, we have shown that a suitable database of known existing sites can be used to train a
381 state-of-the-art deep learning system to accurately find numerous possible new sites of that type (with a
382 high likelihood of success). This comes with a high degree of automation and reasonable processing
383 times, even at a countrywide scale. Second, we showed that these results are transferable to other land-
384 scape types, in this case from Britain to both Italy and Germany. This works well even if the nature of
385 the landscape is significantly different, as shown with the example of terraces in Italy, when specific
386 transfer learning techniques are applied.

387 Third, with the HillfortFinderApp, we present a novel way to make our research results accessible to
388 other archaeologists as a trained neural network, simultaneously inviting them to cooperate online.

389 We believe that the quality of results obtained for hillfort detection are also likely to be applicable to
390 other types of archaeological feature. As a long-term objective, the findings of this project (and similar
391 automatic detection projects) could serve as the basis of a future quality benchmark for the automated
392 identification of archaeological feature using remote sensing data across multiple regions.

394

395 8. Conflict of interest disclosure

396

397 The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in
398 relation to the content of the article.

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